

SYNTHESIS OF α -BROMO- β -KETO-ALDEHYDES FROM OXYMETHYLENE KETONES

BY M. S. MATTA, R. KAUSHAL AND S. S. DESHAPANDE

The action of bromine on sodium oxymethylene ketones in suspension of carbon tetrachloride or in aqueous solution results in the formation of α -bromo- β -keto-aldehydes which are characterised by the formation of anils and semicarbazones. Sodium oxymethylene acetophenone, however, has given α -bromobenzoylacetaldhyde, m. p. 110°. Kurt Meyer's hypothesis of alcoholic bromine addition for the estimation of keto-enolic mixtures is established.

Mehta, Kaushal and Deshapande (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 23, 43) have brought forward evidence in support of the view advanced by Kurt Meyer that the action of bromine on a keto-enolic tautomeric mixture takes place in two stages. Thus in the case of the formyl derivative (III) of a ketone (I), these stages are the following giving finally α -bromo- β -keto aldehyde (VII).

α -Bromo- β -keto-aldehydes seem to be interesting substances as they do not seem to have been described in the literature. Since some of the oxymethylene ketones (IV, R' = H) containing the group CH=CH OH undergo self-condensation to form trisubstituted benzene (Kaushal, Sovani and Deshapande, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 19, 115), the action of bromine has been studied on the sodium compounds (II) as well as on the free ketones (IV). It is convenient to handle sodium compound because in the reaction between a ketone (I) and ethyl formate in presence of metallic sodium, salt (II) of the enol (IV) separates as an ether-insoluble solid, which on subsequent decomposition with cold dilute acid liberates the free oxymethylene ketone. Moreover, as the sodium salt (II) itself absorbs bromine as readily as the oxymethylene ketone (IV), it is advantageous to work on the sodium salt itself thereby avoiding the intermediate stage of generating the oxymethylene ketone and yet the final product will be the same compound (VII) as could be obtained from the free ketone (IV).

When bromine dissolved in carbon tetrachloride is added to the carbon tetrachloride suspension of sodium compound of oxymethylene acetophenone (II, R = Ph, R' = H) in excess under ice cooling, bromine is rapidly absorbed and sodium bromide separates. After distilling off carbon tetrachloride from the filtrate, a thick liquid containing bromine remains from which on standing a colourless crystalline solid separates melting at 110°. This is α -bromobenzoyl acetaldehyde (VII, R = Ph, R' = H) which like other aliphatic aldehydes reacts with two molecules of aniline giving the dianil (VIII, R = Ph; R' = H) melting at 266°. It also forms a semicarbazone containing no bromine of the probable structure (IX, R = Ph; R' = H) melting at 204°. In the formation of semicarbazone, two molecules of semicarbazide react with elimination of one molecule of water and one molecule of hydrobromic acid.

Similarly sodium compound of oxymethylene acetone (II, R = Me; R' = H) by the action of bromine gives a viscous liquid containing bromine which could not be purified. The viscous liquid is the impure α -bromoacetylacetaldehyde (VII, R = Me; R' = H) as it gives reactions of an aldehyde and readily forms a semicarbazone, m.p. 264°. It reacts with aniline like an aliphatic aldehyde giving the dianil (VIII, R = Me; R' = H) melting at 256°.

In the case of oxymethylene methylethyl ketone (IV, R = R' = Me) whose structure has been determined by Kaushal and others (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 18, 479; 1942, 19, 116; 1943, 20, 55), the sodium compound (II, R = R' = Me) is dissolved in water and on addition of bromine water in slight excess a red oil separates which is characterised as α -bromo- α -methylacetylacetaldehyde (VII, R = R' = Me) by its reactions and the formation of the dianil (VIII, R = R' = Me), m.p. 260-61°.

The action of bromine on oxymethylene menthone (X), dissolved in alcohol and neutralised by caustic soda, was studied by Brühl (*Ber.*, 1904, 37, 2176). He obtained an oil which could not be purified by distillation due to its decomposition. To this crude oil he gave the structure (XI).

On treating an aqueous solution of the sodium compound of oxymethylene menthone with bromine water, the same oil, as was obtained by Brühl (*loc. cit.*) separates. The oil could not be purified by distillation and therefore it has been treated directly with aniline when the anil (XIII) separates immediately as a solid, which on crystallisation from glacial acetic acid melts at 270-71° with decomposition. The parent oxymethylene menthone (X) reacts with aniline in presence of anhydrous zinc chloride like an aldehyde to form the dianil (XII) melting at 255-56°.

Thus by the addition of bromine to sodium derivatives of oxymethylene ketone, suspended in dry carbon tetrachloride or dissolved in water, α -bromo- β -keto-aldehydes are formed as coloured viscous liquids which could not be purified by distillation because of their decomposition. In the case of oxymethylene acetophenone, the viscous oil solidifies and the pure solid melts at 110°. These aldehydes are stable and they condense with aniline to form crystalline anils which serve to characterise them. In some cases the semicarbazones of the aldehydes have been prepared and analysed.

It is therefore clearly established that in the estimations of enols in keto-enolic mixtures by the Kurt Meyer's method, bromine first adds to the enol forming a dibromide (VI), the latter then loses hydrobromic acid to form a bromo-ketone (VII).

EXPERIMENTAL

α -Bromobenzoylacetalddehyde (VII, R=Ph; R'=H).—Carefully washed sodium salt of oxymethylene acetophenone (5 g.), prepared by Claissen's method, suspended in carbon tetrachloride (1:5) and bromine dissolved in carbon tetrachloride (1:3) was gradually added in instalments under ice-cooling till the colour of bromine persisted. The sodium bromide formed in the reaction was filtered and on removing the solvent from the filtrate, a red liquid remained, a part of which on distillation under reduced pressure soon solidified and hence the remaining liquid was left overnight when it also solidified: the latter on being rubbed on a porous plate became perfectly white. It could not be crystallised from any organic solvent and was purified by washing with petrol ether, m.p. 110°, yield 1 g [Found: Br (gravimetric), 35.9; (volumetric), 35.6. $C_9H_7O_2Br$ requires Br, 35.2 per cent].

The bromo-aldehyde has got all the reducing properties and gives violet colour with alcoholic ferric chloride and on oxidation with nitric acid gives an oily product.

The dianil (VIII, R=Ph; R'=H) of α -bromobenzoylacetalddehyde was obtained by adding a small piece of anhydrous zinc chloride to the solution of bromo-aldehyde (1.5 g.) and a few drops of aniline in ether, when on rubbing with a glass rod the dianil separated as a pale yellow crystalline mass. It was crystallised from absolute alcohol as needles, m.p. 266-67°, yield 2 g. It contains bromine. (Found: N, 7.5. $C_{21}H_{19}ON_2Br$ requires N, 7.1 per cent).

The *disemicarbazone* (IX, R=Ph; R'-H) of bromobenzoyl acetaldehyde was obtained by adding a little of the aldehyde to a solution of semicarbazide hydrochloride and sodium acetate. On adding a few drops of alcohol it went into solution giving a yellow colour. On rubbing and scratching, the semicarbazone separated as a yellowish white precipitate, which was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from aqueous alcohol, m. p. 204°. (Found: N, 30.2. $C_{11}H_{14}O_3N_6$ requires N, 30.2 per cent).

α -*Bromoacetylacetaldehyde* (VII, R=Me; R'-H) was prepared exactly in the same manner as bromobenzoyl acetaldehyde using 5 g. of organic matter free from sodium oxymethylene acetone, suspended in carbon tetrachloride (1:3). After the addition of bromine was complete, the sodium bromide was filtered and the carbon tetrachloride distilled off when the crude bromo-aldehyde remained as a red coloured liquid yield 2 g. (approx.). It gives all the reactions of an aldehyde and colour reaction with ferric chloride solution.

The *dianil* (VIII, R=Me; R'-H) of bromo-acetaldehyde was prepared by adding aniline, dissolved in ether, to bromo-aldehyde (0.5 g.) in ether. On addition of a little anhydrous zinc chloride condensation with aniline took place and the anil separated as a yellowish precipitate. On crystallisation from absolute alcohol it came out as star shaped needles, m. p 256°. yield 0.3 g. (Found: N, 8.8. $C_{16}H_{17}ON_2Br$ requires N, 8.4 per cent).

The *semicarbazone* of bromoacetylacetaldehyde was prepared in the usual manner as a yellowish crystalline precipitate which after purification melted at 264°.

α -*Bromo- α -methylacetylacetaldehyde* (VII, R=R'-Me).—Ether-washed sodium compound of oxymethylene methylethyl ketone (5 g.), prepared by Claisen's method, was dissolved in water and bromine water was added to it in gradual instalments till permanent red colour had attained. After sometime a red coloured liquid was seen at the bottom. This was extracted with ether and on distilling off the ether, the crude bromo-aldehyde was obtained as a brown liquid, yield nearly 1 g. It gives all the reactions of an aldehyde and is characterised by the formation of its dianil (VIII, R=R'-Me).

The *dianil* (VIII, R=R'-Me) was prepared by adding aniline dropwise to the above bromo-aldehyde when condensation took place with the evolution of heat. The crude product was crystallised from glacial acetic acid as shining crystals, m. p. 260-61°. (Found: N, 8.5; Br, 22.8. $C_{17}H_{19}ON_2Br$ requires N, 8.1; Br, 23.0 per cent).

Sodium salt of oxymethylene menthone (X) was prepared by the method described by Bishop, Claisen and Sinclair (*Annalen*, 1894, 281. 394) using for one molecule of menthone 1.25 moles of amyl formate and 1.25 atoms of sodium. Thus 8 g. of the sodium salt were obtained from 8 g. of menthone.

2-Bromo-2-aldehyde-3-methyl-6-isopropyl-1-cyclohexanone (XI).—To the aqueous solution of the sodium salt of oxymethylene menthone bromine water was gradually added till it did not absorb any more and gave a red colour. It was then extracted with ether and on distilling off the ether the bromo-aldehyde was left as a brown oil which gave the reactions of an aldehyde. It decomposes on distillation.

The sodium salt was suspended in dry carbon tetrachloride and was treated with an excess of bromine in the same solvent like sodium oxymethylene acetophenone. On filtering the sodium bromide formed, the residual liquid after removal of carbon tetrachloride gave the same bromo-aldehyde as an oil. In both the cases bromoaldehyde was characterised by the formation of the anil (XIII).

The *anil* (XIII) was obtained by adding aniline in drops to the bromo-aldehyde (XI). On mixing well condensation took place with evolution of heat and a pale yellow solid separated which on crystallisation from glacial acetic acid came out as fine shining crystals, m.p. 270-71°. (Found : N, 4.6. $C_{17}H_{24}ONBr$ requires N, 4.2 per cent).

Action of Aniline on Oxymethylene Menthone : Formation of Dianil (XII).—On adding a small quantity of anhydrous zinc chloride to a solution of oxymethylene menthone and aniline in ether and rubbing with a glass rod, the dianil (XII) separated as a yellow solid which on crystallisation from alcohol melted at 255-56°. (Found : N, 8.4. $C_{23}H_{30}ON_2$ requires N, 8.0 per cent).